

Neural Style Transfer for Artistic Image Generation

Midhun Krishnan M
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, India
midhunkrishnanmtly@gmail.com

Ms. Ankitha Philip
Asst. Prof. Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, India
ankithaphilip@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract-- In this paper, a technique for separating image content from style using convolutional neural networks (CNNs) is presented. It shows how content, which is connected to high-level elements, and style, which is connected to texture and local details, may be altered separately, enabling the production of artistic images. This study illuminates how our brains process visual information and how we perceive various aspects of images. It implies that CNNs, intended for object detection, naturally discern between image content and style, underlining the role of our visual system in appreciating art.

Keywords— CNNs, VGG19, Style transfer, Image processing, Deep learning, Neural representation

I. INTRODUCTION

There has always been some mystery surrounding how things come together in the world of fine art, where paintings masterfully blend content and aesthetic. This research offers a straightforward but potent artificial system, inspired by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Using neural representations, it skilfully combines the style and content of several images to produce stunning artistic masterpieces. In this study, a novel neural algorithm for creating creative visuals is presented, demystifying the process of human artistic creation in the process.

The field of fine art has consistently captured the attention of both artists and admirers because it is a setting where content and aesthetics meld beautifully to produce works of art that endure. This research reveals an inventive artificial system that is delicately inspired by the capabilities of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), in the aim of unravelling the intricate artistry underlying such creations. It skilfully bridges the gap between the substance of content and the delicacy of style from various images through the use of neural representations, leading to the creation of breath-taking artistic masterpieces.

This study presents a novel method for producing creative visual content while delving deeply into the field of neural artistry. This research's central idea is to use advanced neural algorithms to give the procedure a level of transparency and reproducibility that is unmatched. It offers a revolutionary viewpoint on artistic production, demystifying the previously mysterious facets of the art world while retaining the mesmerizing allure of art's aesthetic qualities.

An evolution in art is being facilitated by the interaction of neural networks and creativity. Using neural networks to power it, artificial intelligence (AI) continuously improves its artistic abilities by taking inspiration from the past and past works. The production of art that transcends conventional

adaptation, adding to the constantly changing field of artistic innovation. The world of art is changing as a result of this fusion of technology and creativity, which gives an idea of the virtually endless potential of AI-driven creativity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Leon A. Gatys et al. [1] present a novel method for transferring artistic style using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Their work demonstrates the separation of content and style representations in CNNs, enabling the synthesis of artistic images by combining the content of one image with the style of another. Deep learning algorithms are employed to create images that closely resemble famous artworks while retaining the original image's content. Additionally, the study explores how this method can be applied to investigate how people perceive and represent art and visual appearance. The research has implications for artistic image generation, fashion trend identification, and neuroscientific studies on image perception. It holds significance in the field of computer vision and has influenced subsequent research in neural style transfer.

C. Zhou et al. [2] in their 2019 study introduced an enhanced style transfer technique that leverages a feedforward neural network for real-time image transformation while preserving content details. This method's key advantage lies in its ability to directly map content images into stylized ones, achieved through the integration of Total Variation (TV) loss, style loss, and content loss. Its significance and influence in the domain of neural style transfer are underscored by its inclusion in related research, where it has been recognized for its capacity to maintain visual content while applying creative styling.

Yongcheng Jing et al. [3] offer a comprehensive analysis of the neural style transfer method in their paper. This analysis delves into the technical aspects of neural style transfer, covering every facet of its development and improvement. The authors emphasize the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and the role of generative adversarial networks (GANs) in enhancing style transfer effects. The study examines the evolution of neural style transfer over time, illustrating its progression toward increased degrees of freedom and improved transfer outcomes. For scholars and professionals seeking to grasp the technical intricacies and the latest advancements in neural style transfer, this paper provides essential insights by addressing the key issues and advancements in the field.

Zhao et al. [4] in their paper, present a novel image synthesis method for style transfer. They address the issue of inappropriate application of style elements in existing

methods by introducing a hybrid approach that combines local and global style loss functions to ensure faithful style transfer while reducing artifacts. This technique has practical applications in various fields, including video stylization, texture synthesis, super-resolution, and font style transfer. The authors and their collaborators contribute to the ongoing research in Neural Style Transfer (NST), enhancing the accuracy of style transfer by mitigating patch transfer errors and preserving intricate style details, ultimately improving the quality of synthesized images.

In their paper, Zhang et al. [5] present a novel approach to image style transfer, focusing on generalizability. Their unified style transfer framework combines style and content encoders, a mixer, and a decoder, enabling the extraction of style and content representations from reference images. Unlike traditional methods that create separate networks for specific style transfers, this framework is designed to build a single transfer network that accommodates various styles and contents. By assuming a common feature encoding method for different styles and contents, the style/content encoder captures a universal representation. Through simultaneous training with multiple styles and contents, this approach simplifies the process and demonstrates its key advantage—generalizability to new styles and contents. This work addresses the limitations of previous style transfer methods, offering the potential for more versatile and adaptable style transfer techniques in the realm of deep neural networks.

III. METHODOLOGY

The central idea behind this approach is to utilize Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to separate and manipulate the content and style of images. It establishes that the CNN, specifically the VGG-Network, inherently captures content and style features in different layers. By understanding and leveraging these feature representations, we enable the synthesis of novel images that combine the content of one image with the artistic style of another.

a. Content and Style Representation

Central to our methodology lies the distinction between content and style representations. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is employed to characterize the content of an image, encapsulating its high-level information. The content representation is acquired by evaluating the loss based on squared differences between the feature maps of the input image and the generated image within a specific layer of the network. This process yields a new image that preserves the original content, although not necessarily in a pixel-wise manner.

Regarding the style representation, our emphasis is on capturing the texture and appearance of the image. To achieve this, we concentrate on contrasting the Gram matrices of feature maps present in various layers of the CNN. The Gram matrix operation plays a pivotal role in the computation of the style loss and is defined as follows:

$$G_{ij}^l = \sum_k F_{ik}^l F_{jk}^l$$

Where G^l is the Gram matrix, F_{ij}^l , is the value of feature map i at position j in layer l , and k ranges over all feature maps in layer l . This operation emphasizes the texture information while minimizing the impact of exact pixel values.

b. Separating and Mixing Content and Style

One of the significant contributions of our approach is the ability to manipulate content and style independently. By adjusting the weighting factors for content and style reconstruction, we can generate images that combine the content of one image with the style of another. The overall loss function, which balances content and style losses, is defined as:

$$L(\text{input}, \text{target}, \text{style}) = \alpha L_{\text{content}} + \beta L_{\text{style}}$$

Where L_{content} represents the content loss, L_{style} represents the style loss, and α and β are weighting factors that control the balance between content and style in the generated image. These parameters enable fine-tuning the artistic style transfer process.

c. Utilizing VGG-Network

In our methodology, we employ the VGG-Network as the CNN of choice for extracting content and style representations. The VGG-Network is pretrained on large image datasets and offers a robust feature extraction capability. We choose different layers in the network for content and style representation, allowing us to manipulate images at various levels of abstraction.

By using the VGG-Network and defining the loss functions, we create a framework for generating images that possess the content of one image and the stylistic features of another. This methodology offers a novel approach to artistic style transfer, combining high-level content and texture in a manner that expands the possibilities for creative image synthesis.

d. Key Takeaways

In conclusion, our approach is based on the principles of neural representations, separating content and style, and employing the VGG-Network to perform artistic style transfer. The equations and concepts presented in this methodology provide a foundation for generating images that blend content and style in a controlled and artistic manner. This opens up avenues for further exploration in image processing and artistic expression.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

In our neural style transfer implementation, we put the previously explained methodology into practice. The provided code snippets are intended to guide readers conceptually through the neural style transfer process. While these code examples are not directly executable, they offer a valuable understanding of how to implement the methodology and combine the content of one image with the stylistic elements of another. By working with these code samples, users can gain firsthand experience in using

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to manipulate content and style, leading to the creation of unique and artistic images. This practical implementation effectively bridges the gap between theory and application, underscoring the method's significance in the fields of computer vision and artistic expression.

A) Required Imports

```
import os
import copy
import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
import torchvision.transforms as transforms
from PIL import Image
from CaffeLoader import loadCaffemodel, ModelParallel

from PIL import Image
from CaffeLoader import loadCaffemodel, ModelParallel
```

B) Load the VGG19 model and configure it for style transfer

```
cnn, layerList = loadCaffemodel(
    params.model_file, params.pooling,
    params.gpu, params.disable_check)
```

C) Preprocessing

```
def preprocess(image_name, image_size):
    image = Image.open(image_name).convert('RGB')
    if type(image_size) is not tuple:
        image_size = tuple([
            int((float(image_size) / max(image.size)) * x)
            for x in (image.height, image.width)
        ])
    Loader = transforms.Compose(
        [transforms.Resize(image_size),
         transforms.ToTensor()])
    rgb2bgr = transforms.Compose([transforms.Lambda(
        lambda x: x[torch.LongTensor([2,1,0])])])
    Normalize = transforms.Compose([transforms.Normalize(
        mean=[103.939, 116.779, 123.68], std=[1,1,1])])
    tensor = Normalize(rgb2bgr(Loader(image) * 255)).unsqueeze(0)
    return tensor
```

D) Construct the Gram Matrix

```
class GramMatrix(nn.Module):

    def forward(self, input):
        B, C, H, W = input.size()
        x_flat = input.view(C, H * W)
        return torch.mm(x_flat, x_flat.t())
```

E) Define an nn Module for Content Loss

```
class ContentLoss(nn.Module):

    def __init__(self, strength, normalize):
        super(ContentLoss, self).__init__()
        self.strength = strength
        self.crit = nn.MSELoss()
        self.mode = 'None'
        self.normalize = normalize

    def forward(self, input):
        if self.mode == 'loss':
            loss = self.crit(input, self.target)
            if self.normalize:
                loss = ScaleGradients.apply(loss, self.strength)
            self.loss = loss * self.strength
        elif self.mode == 'capture':
            self.target = input.detach()
        return input
```

F) Define another nn Module for style loss

```
class StyleLoss(nn.Module):

    def __init__(self, strength, normalize):
        super(StyleLoss, self).__init__()
        self.target = torch.Tensor()
        self.strength = strength
        self.gram = GramMatrix()
        self.crit = nn.MSELoss()
        self.mode = 'None'
        self.blend_weight = None
        self.normalize = normalize

    def forward(self, input):
        self.G = self.gram(input)
        self.G = self.G.div(input.nelement())
        if self.mode == 'capture':
            if self.blend_weight == None:
                self.target = self.G.detach()
            elif self.target.nelement() == 0:
                self.target = self.G.detach().mul(self.blend_weight)
            else:
                self.target = self.target.add(self.blend_weight, self.G.detach())
        elif self.mode == 'loss':
            loss = self.crit(self.G, self.target)
            if self.normalize:
                loss = ScaleGradients.apply(loss, self.strength)
            self.loss = self.strength * loss
        return input
```

G) Define a different module for Total Variation Loss

```
class TVLoss(nn.Module):

    def __init__(self, strength):
        super(TVLoss, self).__init__()
        self.strength = strength

    def forward(self, input):
        self.x_diff = input[:, :, 1:, :] - input[:, :, :-1, :]
        self.y_diff = input[:, :, :, 1] - input[:, :, :, :-1]
        self.loss = self.strength * (
            torch.sum(torch.abs(self.x_diff)) +
            torch.sum(torch.abs(self.y_diff)))
        return input
```

V. RESULTS

To commence the neural style transfer process, we initiate by specifying the content and style images, and subsequently assign associated weighting factors to each. This pivotal step allows us to define the influence of content and style in the final output image. These weighting factors serve as the guiding principles, determining the emphasis placed on preserving the content of the content image while infusing it with the artistic style of the style image.

It's imperative to note that the number of iterations chosen for this process significantly impacts the computational time required for generating the resultant output image. In practice, a higher iteration count entails a proportionate increase in the time and computational resources dedicated to the image generation process. This trade-off between iteration count and computational intensity underscores the need for a balanced approach, considering both the desired output quality and the available resources. By strategically tuning these parameters, we can achieve the desired balance between efficiency and the creation of visually striking images that seamlessly blend content and style.

Fig. 1 Content Image

Fig. 2 Style Image

Then we specify the weights for the images and set the iteration count for the style transfer.

Fig. 3 Results

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, the methodology of neural style transfer presents an intriguing and highly effective means of

seamlessly merging the content of one image with the artistic style of another. This process hinges on the precise definition of content and style losses, which are skillfully utilized to iteratively optimize an input image. The result is a captivating array of images that elegantly blend both content and style elements, offering a harmonious visual experience.

Furthermore, the foundation of this methodology in convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and the use of the Gram matrix reveal deep insights into the potential of deep learning for artistic and aesthetic image manipulation. This profound understanding not only elevates the realms of artistry but also extends its applications to the broader fields of computer vision and image processing. As a pivotal technique, neural style transfer acts as a bridge between the realms of art and technology, promising exciting opportunities for innovation and exploration in the evolving landscape of visual media.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. A. Gatys, A. S. Ecker and M. Bethge, "Image Style Transfer Using Convolutional Neural Networks," 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016, pp. 2414-2423, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.265.
- [2] Zhou, Chang, Zhenghong Gu, Yu Gao, and Jin Wang. 2019. "An Improved Style Transfer Algorithm Using Feedforward Neural Network for Real-Time Image Conversion" Sustainability 11, no. 20: 5673. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205673>
- [3] Y. Jing, Y. Yang, Z. Feng, J. Ye, Y. Yu and M. Song, "Neural Style Transfer: A Review," in IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics, vol. 26, no. 11, pp. 3365-3385, 1 Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TVCG.2019.2921336.
- [4] H. -H. Zhao, P. L. Rosin, Y. -K. Lai, M. -G. Lin and Q. -Y. Liu, "Image Neural Style Transfer With Global and Local Optimization Fusion," in IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 85573-85580, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2922554.
- [5] Y. Zhang, Y. Zhang and W. Cai, "A Unified Framework for Generalizable Style Transfer: Style and Content Separation," in IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, vol. 29, pp. 4085-4098, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIP.2020.2969081.